

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

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THE HISTORICAL GEOGRAPHY OF KARABAKH IN AZERBAIJAN

Abstract:

This article examines the etymological meaning of the name "Karabakh," a region belonging to the Karabakh region of Azerbaijan, and analyzes the origin of this name in Turkish. The article provides information on the historical geography of the Karabakh region. It also provides information on the administrative-territorial system and the regional interregional system established by the Tsarist government during the Züütü period.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Karabakh region, etymology, historical geography, region, search.

Introduction

The beginning of the twentieth century represents one of the most significant periods in the socio-political history of Northern Azerbaijan. This period can be regarded as the time when the foundations were laid for the establishment of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, the first state to emerge within the Turkic-Muslim world and one that opened a golden page in the history of Azerbaijan. Therefore, the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, which embodied the state traditions of our history and emerged as the political and legal successor of our medieval states, was the logical outcome of the political and ideological struggle of the Azerbaijan Turks, who passed through complex and challenging political processes.

The early twentieth century was also characterized by political and cultural awakening in Azerbaijani history, as well as by the honorable historical path of our intellectuals, political figures, and freedom fighters who struggled to protect our lands and historical territories. This period is further marked by harsh political and socio-economic conditions and by the life-and-death struggle of our people, statesmen, and freedom fighters.

Karabakh, an integral part of Azerbaijan, has long served as one of the main centers of the ethnocultural heritage of our people and is recognized as the cradle of ancient Azerbaijani civilization. From ancient times, Karabakh has been one of the most significant regions of Azerbaijan in terms of political, socio-economic, and cultural development and is considered among the earliest centers of world civilization. The discovery of a lower jawbone belonging to an ancient human in the Azikh Cave during archaeological excavations conducted in the Karabakh region of Northern Azerbaijan proved that this territory, along with Azerbaijan as a whole, is one of the oldest human settlements in the world.

Following the occupation of the Caucasus, including the territories of Northern Azerbaijan, in the first half of the nineteenth century, Tsarist Russia forcibly resettled primarily Armenians and other Christian populations to various regions, including Karabakh, in order to create an ethnic foundation favorable to its interests. Seeking to consolidate its occupation policy in the

South Caucasus and particularly in Karabakh, the empire primarily aimed to expel the Turkic-Muslim population from the region and replace it with inhabitants belonging to the Christian faith.

Having resettled Armenians in the South Caucasus, the Tsarist government, taking into account the insufficient number of Armenians brought to the region by the end of the nineteenth century, signed a decree in 1899 on the settlement of Slavic Christians of Orthodox faith in the South Caucasus. By issuing this decree, the Tsarist authorities implicitly acknowledged that the number of Armenians previously relocated to the region was inadequate. While attempting to Christianize the South Caucasus, Tsarist Russia relied on exaggerated demographic estimates of the Armenian population and initially concentrated on their settlement. However, being aware of the inaccuracy of these figures, the imperial government was compelled to adopt a new decree in 1899 to implement another project. Thus began the resettlement of Orthodox Christians into the South Caucasus. Nevertheless, this project failed to yield tangible results due to the socio-political developments unfolding in the Caucasus.

The territories of Erivan, Nakhchivan, and Karabakh—among the oldest regions of Azerbaijan—became victims of the hostile policies of Tsarist Russia from the early nineteenth century onward. These territories were situated at the highlands of the Lesser Caucasus mountain range and along the borders of the Ottoman Empire and the Qajar State, areas of particular strategic concern to Tsarist Russia. This geographical reality further increased the strategic significance of Erivan, Nakhchivan, and Karabakh for the empire in terms of defense against these neighboring powers. Consequently, from the beginning of the nineteenth century, Tsarist Russia sought to remove the local Turkic-Muslim population from these lands, as the majority of this population shared common ethnic and religious origins with the Turks living in both the Qajar State and the Ottoman Empire.

1. The Etymology of the Name "Karabakh"

When examining the etymological meaning of the word *Karabakh*, which was given to this region of Azerbaijan in the early Middle Ages, research findings indicate that the term is of Azerbaijani-Turkic origin.

References to the etymological meaning of the name *Karabakh* appear in historical sources dating back to the early Middle Ages (7th century). While the Karabakh region of Azerbaijan initially denoted a specific locality as a historical and geographical concept, the term was later applied to a broader geographical territory of Azerbaijan. According to scholarly assessments presented by researchers, the name *Karabakh* is derived from the Azerbaijani words *kara* and *bağ*. The combination of the words *kara* and *bağ* has an ancient historical background, as old as the Azerbaijani Turks themselves. In Azerbaijani Turkish (as well as in other Turkic languages), the word *kara* conveys meanings such as “dense,” “thick,” “large,” “magnificent,” “dark,” and similar connotations. In this context, the term *Karabakh* signifies “black garden,” that is, “a large garden,” “a dense garden,” “a rich garden,” and similar meanings. [6, p.11]

Many authors have noted that in early historical sources (up until the 12th–13th centuries), the word *Karabakh* appears under various distinct names. The region was referred to as Gerger, Uti, Utik, Udin, Otena, Kara, Karalar, Arsak, and other designations. [2, p.11]

In some research studies, the origin of the term *Karabakh* is also linked to the names of tribes living in the region. Archaeologist Rashid Goyushov, in his work *A Journey into the Past of Karabakh*, associates the origin of the term *Karabakh* with the name of the Turkic tribe *Gargar* and provides information that in ancient and early medieval centuries, part of Karabakh was known as the “Land of the Gargars.” [4, p.5]

In the joint research article by historians Yagub Mahmudov and Karim Shukurov, it is concluded that the word *Arsak*, historically attributed to the Karabakh region since ancient times, corresponds in meaning to the Turkic word *Arsak*, signifying “brave,” “valiant,” or “Sak man.” [7, p.31]

Since the “a” sound in Azerbaijani Turkish does not fully exist in some other languages, it was often pronounced and written in different forms in many sources. Thus, instead of appearing exactly as *Arsak*, the term has been recorded with varying orthographic forms.

A.S. Sumbatzade and A.A. Rahmani note in their works that the term *Karabakh* carries meanings such as “people and garden,” “great garden,” “pleasant garden,” and similar interpretations. This region largely comprised the historical territory of Caucasian Albania, encompassing primarily the provinces of Arsak, Syunik, Uti, Sakasena, and Paytakaran, and was also known by these designations.

Information provided in the scholarly works of the period indicates that the etymological name of the Karabakh region of Northern Azerbaijan dates back to the early medieval era and is of Turkic origin. [16, pp.145–146]

2. The Administrative–Territorial Governance System of Azerbaijani Karabakh

Although the political borders of the Karabakh region remained generally stable throughout history, they

underwent certain changes depending on socio-political developments in the area.

In the early Middle Ages, the Karabakh region (the provinces of Uti and Artsakh) formed part of the Caucasian Albanian state. In antiquity, the territory of Karabakh encompassed the Albanian provinces of Uti, Paytakaran, and Arsak (Artsakh). The lands of Karabakh, situated between the Kur and Araz rivers, were inhabited predominantly by local tribes—Albanians, Utis, Gargars, and Savdeys—as well as foreign tribes such as the Masguts, Sakas, Gels, and Bals. [18, p.64]

Generally, the territory of the Caucasian Albanian state had, since ancient times, been inhabited by Albanian, Gargar, Khazar, Gugar, and other local Turkic-speaking tribes. [12, p.23]

The Arab campaigns that began in the 7th century resulted in the conquest of Albania. Beginning from the 8th century, as in all regions of Azerbaijan, a new era commenced in Karabakh as well, and Karabakh became the northern center of the Caliphate. [15, p.58]

During the period of feudal states in the 9th–11th centuries, Karabakh remained an integral part of Arran and played an important role in the political, socio-economic, and cultural life of these states. Subsequently, Karabakh, together with Arran, came under the rule of the Seljuk State and later the Azerbaijani Atabegs.

After the Mongol invasion of Azerbaijan, the Karabakh region fell under the administration of Mongol emirs and became one of the political centers of Khwarazmshah Jalal al-Din and later of the Hulagu rulers. [2, pp.10–11]

At the end of the 14th century, Karabakh turned into a battlefield of Timur’s campaigns, and in the 15th century it became a theater of conflict between the Timurids and the Qara Qoyunlu. From 1410 onwards, the Azerbaijani territories south of the Kur River, including Karabakh, came under the domination of the Qara Qoyunlu. [25, p.119]

After the collapse of the Qara Qoyunlu State in 1467, Karabakh was incorporated into the territories of the Aq Qoyunlu State.

During the Safavid period, according to the administrative-territorial division of Azerbaijan, part of the Karabakh region was under the administration of the Ganja Beylerbeylik, while another part was governed by the Chukhur-Saad Beylerbeylik and administered by Qajar tribal rulers. [13, p.237]

In the early 16th century (1501), the Karabakh Beylerbeylik—one of the administrative regions established by the Azerbaijani Safavid State—covered Astabad, Javanshir, Bargushad, Gazakh, and Shamshadil from the 17th century to the early 18th century. [3, p.33]

The Karabakh Beylerbeylik was governed by the Ziyadoghlu dynasty, whose representative was Sultan Shahverdi. [22, p.59]

Founded in the early years of the reign of Shah Ismail I, the Karabakh Beylerbeylik initially belonged to the descendants of Kara Piri Bey Qajar and became the property of the Ziyadoghlu branch of the Qajars only in 1554. Except for the periods of Ottoman conquests (1590–1606 and 1725–1735) and the final years of the

reign of Shah Abbas I (1587–1629) together with the early years of Shah Safi's reign (1629–1642), the Ziyadoghlu governed the Karabakh Beylerbeylik until the collapse of the Safavid State and the rise of Nadir Shah Afshar. [25, pp.285–286]

The Karabakh Beylerbeylik, whose administrative center was the city of Ganja, covered a vast territory. The work *Tazkirat al-Muluk* lists nine districts under the Karabakh Beylerbeylik administered by governors: Zeyem, Barda, Aghstafa, Javanshir, Bargushad, Kara-Aghach (located in the Kakheti region of Georgia), Lori and Pambek, Arazbar, Bayazidli, Simavi, and Terkur. [9, p.67]

Some sources state that during the Safavid period, the Karabakh Beylerbeylik “was located between the Kur and Araz rivers and extended from Aghstafa to Ordubad.” [20, p.241]

The Safavids united the territories of Karabakh entirely under the Karabakh or Ganja Beylerbeylik. During the Safavid-Ottoman wars (1514–1555, 1578–1590, etc.), Karabakh repeatedly changed hands. After the 1590 treaty, a detailed register on the Karabakh territories was compiled, and in 1593 these lands became part of the Ottoman Empire. According to this information, the Ganja-Karabakh province was divided into five *sanjaks* and thirty-six districts (*mahals*). In terms of religious affiliation, 61% of the population was Muslim, while the remainder was non-Muslim. The non-Muslim population consisted of Albanians who had converted to Christianity during the 5th-century Caucasian Albanian state. When the territories of Azerbaijan were divided among Iran, Russia, and the Ottoman Empire in the first quarter of the 18th century, Karabakh remained under Ottoman rule. [8, p.168]

In the 18th century, an independent khanate—the Karabakh Khanate—was established in the Karabakh region. The Karabakh Khanate was administratively divided into 21 *mahals* (districts), including five Christian *melik* principalities. The *mahals* were governed by *naibs* (deputies), while the *meliks* administered the *melikdoms* within the mahals. During the period of the Karabakh Khanate, there was one city and 638 villages in Karabakh. The population, which reached 90,000 people, was distributed across 18,500 households. [12, pp. 4, 93]

At the beginning of the 19th century, the Sisian region under Melik Tanri's authority was located in the southeastern part of the khanate. At the time of the abolition of the khanate, 303 families (87 tax-paying and 116 non-tax-paying) lived in nine villages subordinate to this region. According to the same source, it is known that in earlier periods around 2,000 families resided in this area. Following the occupation of the khanate by Russia and during the First Russo-Iranian War, the population of the region abandoned their homes and migrated to various parts of Azerbaijan and other countries. [11, p.239]

The 18th-century Azerbaijani historian Mirza Jamal Javanshir (Karabakhi), in his work *The History of Karabakh*, provides highly valuable information regarding the political boundaries of Karabakh. He writes:

“According to ancient historical sources, the boundaries of the Karabakh province are as follows: from the south, the Araz River up to the Khudafarin Bridge; from the east, the Kur River, which joins the Araz River near the village of Javad and flows into the Caspian Sea; from the north, the Goran River, extending to the Kur River along the border of Karabakh with Yelizavetpol (present-day Ganja), and the Kur River flows through many areas before joining the Araz River; and from the west, the high Karabakh mountains known as Kushbek, Salvarti, and Erikli.” [5, pp.4–5]

The information provided by Mirza Jamal Javanshir regarding the territorial boundaries of Karabakh, based on ancient historical sources, clearly reflects the borders of Karabakh in the 18th century. On the basis of these data, it is possible to determine the administrative units included in the Karabakh region during the administrative-territorial division carried out in the South Caucasus following the occupation of Northern Azerbaijan by Tsarist Russia. In the *Caucasian Calendar* of 1855, while describing the borders of the Dereleyez district, reference is made to “the Kushbilek (Kushbek) mountains near the Arpa River, close to the Karabakh borders, and the Sichaksu area where thermal springs exist today.”

This helps to define the borders of the Karabakh region of Northern Azerbaijan. The information presented in the *Caucasian Calendar* is consistent with the data in Mirza Javanshir's *History of Karabakh*. From all these records, it becomes clear that at the beginning of the 20th century, the political geography of Azerbaijan's Karabakh region consisted of four districts: Shusha, Zangezur, Jabrayil, and Javanshir (which had been renamed Jabrayil from 1904 onward).

After the occupation of Northern Azerbaijan by Tsarist Russia in the 19th century, an administrative-territorial governance system began to be established in accordance with the imperial policy. [17, p.369]

In the 19th century, Tsarist Russia incorporated Azerbaijan's Karabakh region into various administrative governance systems. It is known that the commandant administrative system established in 1828 failed to respond to the need to strengthen the political foundations of Tsarist rule in the South Caucasus, including Northern Azerbaijan. Consequently, on 10 April 1840, a law on administrative reform in the South Caucasus was enacted. Under this law, the commandant administrative system was abolished, and instead an all-Russian administrative system was introduced. [19, p.132]

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According to the 1897 data, the boundaries of the districts belonging to the Karabakh region of Northern Azerbaijan were as follows. During the period of the

Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, the territories of these districts, with minor exceptions, remained unchanged. The Shusha district of the Karabakh region bordered the districts of Javanshir, Goychay, Javad, Jabrayil, and Zangezur. Its administrative center was the city of Shusha. The Shusha district was incorporated into the Caspian Province in 1841. From 1846, it was subordinated to the Shamakhi, Baku, and Yelizavetpol (Ganja) governorates, and from 1867 onward, it became part of the Yelizavetpol (Ganja) governorate. Shusha district was divided into the regions of Meghri, Kebirli, Zangezur, Javanshir, Chilabord, and Varanda. By the decree of December 1867, the Zangezur and Javanshir districts were separated from Shusha district and turned into independent administrative units. The district was governed by a district chief, his deputy, treasurer, land valuation officers, and city police. A district court was also established. The district covered an area of 4,911 square kilometers, with a population of 140,740 (1897). During this period, the districts of Northern Azerbaijan were administered by a district chief, deputy, and secretary. [14, p.124]

In the 1904 edition of the *Collection of Materials on the Description of the Territories and Peoples of the Caucasus*, published in Tiflis from 1881 by the Caucasian Educational District, the boundaries of the Zangezur district of the Karabakh region are described as follows: “To the east and northeast, it borders the Shusha and Jabrayil districts; to the north, the Javanshir district; to the west and southwest, the Aresh district; and it borders Nuha, Goychay, Nakhchivan, and Sharur-Daralayaz districts, the Erivan governorate, Southern Azerbaijan, Yelizavetpol district, and Zagatala; to the south and southeast, the Araz River, which forms the border between Russia and Iran.” The district was established in 1873 within the Yelizavetpol governorate. Its administrative center was the settlement of Goris. The district covered an area of 3,212.5 square kilometers. [23, p.182]

In 1883, two new districts—Jabrayil and Javanshir—were established within the Yelizavetpol province. The Jabrayil district, bordering Shusha, Zangezur, Javad districts and Southern Azerbaijan, had an area of 3,332 square kilometers, with its center in the settlement of Jabrayil. The Javanshir district, bordering Aresh, Yelizavetpol, Zangezur, Shusha districts and the Erivan governorate, had an area of 5,497 square kilometers, with its administrative center in Tartar. The activities of both districts ceased in 1929. [4, p.38]

The *1903 Military District Map of the Caucasus*, drawn in 1903, is of great importance as it provides a general depiction of the historical geography of Azerbaijan in the second half of the 19th and early 20th centuries. According to the data on the map, the main territories of Northern Azerbaijan formed part of the Baku, Yelizavetpol, and Erivan governorates. The Baku province consisted of six districts (Baku, Guba, Shamakhi, Goychay, Javad, Lankaran). The Yelizavetpol governorate consisted of eight districts (Yelizavetpol, Aresh, Nuha, Javanshir, Kazakh, Shusha, Jabrayil (Karyagin), Zangezur) and one district unit (Zagatala). The total area of the Yelizavetpol governorate was

39,982 square kilometers. In 1905, two temporary general governorates were established within the territory of the Yelizavetpol governorate. One included the Zangezur, Javanshir, and Shusha districts, while the other covered the remaining territories. The Erivan governorate was divided into seven districts (Erivan, Nakhchivan, Sharur-Daralayaz, New Bayazid, Surmeli, Echmiadzin, and Gyumri). The historical Azerbaijani territories of Erivan, Nakhchivan, Goycha Mahal, Sharur-Daralayaz, and New Bayazid were incorporated into the Erivan governorate; Borchali belonged to the Tiflis governorate; and Derbend belonged to the Dagestan governorate. [14, p.119]

On this map, the administrative territory of the Karabakh region consisted of the districts of Shusha, Zangezur, Javanshir, and Jabrayil, which were part of the Yelizavetpol (Ganja) governorate. From 1868 until the establishment of the Soviet administrative system in Azerbaijan (1920), the Karabakh region remained part of the Yelizavetpol governorate, whose administrative center was the city of Yelizavetpol (Ganja). Even during the period of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic in 1918, its territorial boundaries remained unchanged. [5, p.76]

At the beginning of the twentieth century, the spread of the revolutionary movement that swept across Russia to Azerbaijan compelled the Tsarist government to extend the “Temporary Statute,” adopted in 1881, to the cities and districts of Azerbaijan as well. Thus, beginning from September 1903, this statute was also applied in Karabakh. This meant that the governors of Baku and Yelizavetpol were authorized to impose fines of up to 500 rubles or sentences of up to three months’ imprisonment on those who participated in meetings and demonstrations deemed contrary to “public order and stability,” as well as on other individuals who “violated” the enhanced security regulations. [1, p.98]

In 1909, the governor began reorganizing the villages, rural communities, and police posts in the districts into separate units, and this work was completed in 1910. [21, p.1]

In connection with the administrative land division and governance system implemented in the Russian Empire from the second half of the 19th century onward, the Russian Tsar enacted the “Rural Communities Law” in 1865. Through this law, beys and aghas were removed from the administrative-judicial affairs of the villages, and unified rural administrations were established to govern village affairs. [24, p.4]

This administrative land division system was reintroduced in the districts of the Karabakh region in 1910. In 1910, four rural communities were established in the Shusha district. The first administrative unit included the following village communities: Shushakend, Tashaly, Halfali, Keshishkend, Malibeyli, Pirjamal, Sizinik, Khanazakh, Kishlak, Chanakhchi, and Khankendi. The second administrative unit included the following: Tug, Taghaver, Tagh, Sus, Arpavand, Chertaz, Qajar, Gulabli, Yenikend, Skobelev, and Kagarzin. The third administrative unit consisted of the following village communities: Aghdam, Shelli, Giyasli, Goytepe, Shikhlar, Garvand, Zangishal, Karahanli, Sarijali-Guzanli, (Lemberan area) Karavelli, Khanabad, and Nevruzlu.

The fourth administrative unit included: Hindarkh, Arazbarli, Merzili, Minakhorlu, Husulu, Halfaradin, Karadolag, Nevruzlu, Khojavand (Lemberan area), Ilagilar, and Lemberan.

In another district of Karabakh—Zangezur—four rural communities were also established. The first administrative unit included the following: Alikulukend, Aypilin, Enealut, Ahlatian, Pazarchay, Vagudi, Goris, Darabas, Pirnaut, Sisian, Tatev, Uz, Hinzirek, Hot, Shalat, Sheki, Shinger, Shikhtar, and Yayji. The second included: Bayandur, Gerenzu, Cagauz, Chijimli, Digh, Kaledere, Karakishlak, Malibeyli, Mollalar, Muslimanlar, Bichenis, Safiyan, Seyidler, Hezinavar, and Shahsuvarli. The third included: Aliyanli, Alikuluashaghi, Archevan, Babali, Gal, Karar, Dondarli, Godekler, Kazikurdali, Kerdjalanli, Mammadli, Mollin, Norashen, Ohtar, Sarali, Sariyatak, Sofulu, Ucanis, Hendek, Helec, Hojavan, Shikhavin. The fourth administrative unit included the following villages: Alidere, Astazur, Bartaz, Vartanzur, Gyagyalin, Gudgum, Terzili, Jhangirbeyli, Kiryatag, Kever, Levaz, Mehri, Nuvadi, Okchu, Pirchevan, Raband, Tirin, Ordakhli, Zangilan, Shikhauz, and Isganderbeyli.

In the Javanshir district, three rural communities were established. The first administrative unit included the following villages: Barda, Gerene, Dorbatli, Ayridjin, Khoruzlu, Karamanli, Yevlakh, Karadaghli, Borsunlu, Sarov, and Talish. The second unit included: Aghali, Alpout, Khanaragh, Kocharly, Namirli, Hankarakoyunlu, Sahlabad, Lekli, Shirvanli, Maragali, Mamirli, and Kilichli. The third unit consisted of: Janyatak, Kasapet, Hasanriz, Tavshanli, Kichik Karabey, Orlovo-Denisov, Mingrel, Boyakhmedli, Sirhavend, Chirakhli, Imaragarand, Avaryan, Ayrim, Keshdag, Esrik, and Koturlu.

By 1904, two rural communities had been established in the Karyagin district (later known as Jabrayil). In the first administrative unit were the following villages: Abdurrahmanbeyli, Aghali, Alihanli, Banazur, Bahmanli, Hadrut, Horadiz, Karakelli, Kargapazar, Karyagin, Karim Beyli, Mahmudlu, Suleymanli, Taghassir, Shahsevan, Edilin, and Karahanbeyli. The second administrative unit included: Jabrayil, Tashkesen, Kuchak, Maralyan, Ahmedli, Aragil, Aghjakend, Soltanli, Kovshudlu, Aghali, Khanlyk, Hojik, and Mefruzlu. [21, p.4]

The total area of the Karabakh region of Northern Azerbaijan was 4,911 square kilometers; the area of Shusha, which belonged to the Yelizavetpol (Ganja) governorate, was 3,212.5 square kilometers; the Javanshir district covered 5,497 square kilometers; and the Jabrayil district covered 3,332 square kilometers. During this period, the total area of the Karabakh region was 16,952.5 square kilometers. [17, p.4]

CONCLUSION

The etymological meaning of the name of Karabakh, one of the regions of Northern Azerbaijan, is recorded in historical sources dating back to the early Middle Ages. The etymological origin of this name belongs to the Azerbaijani Turks. The research conducted

in this article shows that despite the mass resettlement of Christian Armenian and Slavic populations into the region by the Tsarist government, the majority of the population in Karabakh at the beginning of the twentieth century still consisted of Azerbaijani Turks.

The Bolsheviks, who overthrew the Tsarist government in Russia in 1917, continued the previous policy of Christianization in the South Caucasus. During the Soviet period, they deported the Turkic-Muslim population from the entirety of the Zangezur and Shusha districts of Karabakh, as well as from parts of the Jabrayil and Javanshir districts. In 1921, the Zangezur district of the Karabakh region was completely transferred to the newly established Republic of Armenia. At present, there is no longer a single Turkic-Muslim population living in a large part of the Karabakh region.

In order to implement this policy, both the Tsarist government and, later, the Soviet Union sought to employ only individuals of Christian faith within the administrative-territorial governance system they introduced in the South Caucasus. Although some Russian authors attribute this to an alleged shortage of intellectuals among the Muslim population of the Caucasus at the time, in reality this was not the case. Despite only a few years having passed since the proclamation of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic in 1918, Azerbaijan possessed a considerable intellectual community. With few exceptions, the imperial government did not allow these intellectuals to participate in governance. On the contrary, many of them were eliminated during the establishment of the Soviet Union.

One of the reasons why the Tsarist government did not involve Azerbaijani Turks in the governance system at that time was its policy of complete Christianization of the Caucasus. The Tsarist authorities were well aware that the Azerbaijani Turks—indigenous people of the Caucasus, whose identity was administratively labeled as “Tatars” in accordance with imperial policy—would strongly oppose such a strategy.

References:

1. Azərbaycan tarixi. Yeddi cildə V cild (1900-1920-ci illər), Bakı, Elm, 2008.
2. Əfəndiyev O, Azərbaycan Səfəvilər dövləti, Bakı: Şərq-Qərb, 2007.
3. Göyüşov R, Qarabağın keçmişinə səyahət, Bakı, Azərneşr, 1993.
4. Qarabağnamələr. İkinci kitab. Bakı: Yazıçı, 1991, s. 450.
5. Mahmudov Y, Şükürov K, Qarabağ. Real tarix, faktlar, sənədlər, Bakı, Təhsil Nəşriyyatı, 2009.
6. Məmmədov N, Azərbaycanın Xankəndi şəhərinin tarixi, Bakı, Təhsil, 2011.
7. Muradov V, Azərbaycan xalçaları Qarabağ qrupu, Bakı, Elm, 2010.
8. Musalı N, “Səfəvilər zamanında Qarabağ bəylərbəyliyi yaradılması və onun inzibati quruluşu”, Qarabağ dünən, bu gün və sabah V Respublika elmi-əməli konfransının materialları, Bakı, Qarabağ Azadlıq Təşkilatı, 2006.
9. Musalı N, “Şah İsmayıl Xətai və Qarabağ bəyləri”, Qarabağ folkloru: problemlər,

perspektivlərmövzusunda II Respublika Elmi Konfransının materialları, Bakı, Nurlan, 2013,

10. Mustafazadə T, Qarabağ xanlığı, Bakı, Sabah, 2010.

11. Nəcəfli T, “Qarabağ XVI əsrdə”, Qarabağ dünən, bu gün və sabah V ümumrespublika elmi-əməli konfransının materialları, Bakı, QAT, 2008.

12. Pirişev V, Azərbaycanın tarixi-siyasi coğrafiyası, Bakı, Müəllim nəşriyyatı, 2006.

13. Vəlixanlı N, Ərəb xilafəti və Azərbaycan, Bakı, Azərbaycan Dövlət Nəşriyyatı, 1993.

14. Attar A, Karabağ sorunu kapsamında ermeniler ve ermeni siyaseti, Ankara, 2005.

15. Mustafazade T. Karabağ Hanlığı, çeviren Sebahattin Ş, İstanbul, İQ Kültür Sanat Yayıncılık, 2014.

16. Сумбатзаде А, Азербайджанцы – этногенез и формирование народа. Баку, Элм, 1990.

17. Кавказский календарь на 1855 год. Издань по распоряжению Главноначальствующаго гражданской частию на Кавказе. Под ред. Е. Кондратенко. Тифлись, 1854.

18. Мамедов Т, Кавказская Албания в IV-VII вв, Баку, 1993.

19. Мильман А, Политический строй Азербайджана в XIX – начале XX вв. Баку, 1966.

20. Павлов И, Хроника времен Сефевидов (сочинения Мухфммед Масума «Исфакхани-ас-сийас», Moskva, 1993.

21. Памятная книга Елисаветпольской губернии на 1910 годъ, Подъ редакцией Секретаря Комитета И.П.Бабенко, Типография Канцелярий Наместника Е.И.В. на Кавказъ, Тифлись, 1910.

22. Рахмани А, Азербайджан: границы и административное деление в конце XVI-XVII вв. Азербайджан, Баку, Елм, 1987.

23. Сборник материалов для описания местностей и племен Кавказа, Тифлись, Типография К.Козловскаго, 1904.

24. Умаев А, Проникновение капитала в сельское хозяйство Азербайджана в 1883-1914 гг. Автореф. канд. дис. Баку, 1963.

25. Хунджи Фазлуллах ибн Рузбихан. Тарих-и алам-арай амини. Пер. с.англ. на русский Т.А.Минорский, Баку, Елм, 1987.